

January 2025

Press Release

Post Quantum Cryptography Framework for Energy Aware Contexts

PQ-REACT Open Call #1: Develop

After the successful implementation of the PQ-REACT Open Call#1-Develop and the conclusion of the evaluation, the PQ-REACT project presents the beneficiaries of the first Open Call-Develop.

Five organisations across Europe are embarking on the PQ-REACT journey towards a faster and smoother transition from classical to post-quantum cryptography through their innovative and impactful proposals. Over the next six months, the beneficiaries will closely collaborate with the PQ-REACT project to bring their innovative ideas to life.

The beneficiaries:

CREAPLUS (Use case 1 winner)

Project tile: **Analysis and Optimisation of PQC Algorithms for Firmware Signing**

Funded by
the European Union

Decent Cybersecurity (Use case 3 winner)

Project title: **CRISP-Q**

EIGHTBELLS LTD (Use case 2 winner)

EIGHTBELLS
Independent Research & Consultancy

Project title: **Quantum-Agile 5G Core / QA5G**

Tecnalia (Use case 4 winner)

tecnalia

MEMBER OF BASQUE RESEARCH
& TECHNOLOGY ALLIANCE

Project title: **QUIET - QRISP for Measuring the Security of Lattice-Based Cryptosystems**

Funded by
the European Union

Vicomtech (Use case 2 winner)

vicomtech

MEMBER OF BASQUE RESEARCH
& TECHNOLOGY ALLIANCE

Project title: **Q-PROTECT: 5G Quantum Security Transition**

Learn more about the PQ-REACT Open Call#1 beneficiaries [here!](#)

Follow PQ-REACT

@PQREACT

@PQ-REACT

@PQ-REACT-EU-PROJECT

Funded by
the European Union